

THE NEEDS FOR DEVELOPING THE SABU-SABU METHOD TO INCREASE THE READING INTEREST OF STUDENTS THROUGH DIGITAL LIBRARIES

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Abstract

The literacy level in Indonesia is still low, namely ranking 62nd out of 70 countries with an average literacy score of 397 compared to developed countries of 493. This is proven by the low reading interest of students in schools in Indonesia. The research methodology used qualitative with a sample of 43 students from a population of 110. From the research results, it was found that student's interest in reading at SMAN 19 Tebo was still low. For this reason, it is necessary to develop a method that can increase student's interest in reading at the high school level, especially at SMAN 19 Tebo.

Keywords: reading literacy, interest in reading, digital library, Industrial Revolution 4.0

INTRODUCTION

Interest in reading is one of the factors that can increase an individual's ability to face the challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0. By reading, individuals can obtain new information and knowledge that can be used to understand and overcome the various challenges they face (Widiana et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023; Link et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2018; Boerma et al., 2018).

In theory, it is proven that interest in reading can improve problem-solving and critical-thinking skills (Yulian, 2021; Mohammadi et al., 2020; Ng et al., 2021; Öztürk et al., 2019; Li et al., 2022; Mohseni et al., 2020; Holbert, 2019). These two skills are provisions for individuals to face the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0.

However, in reality, as time goes by and the industrial revolution, students' interest in reading books is getting lower. Internal and external factors can cause students' low interest

in reading (Hebbecker et al., 2019; Toste et al., 2020; Kanonire et al., 2020; Ives et al., 2022; Miyamoto, 2023; Locher et al., 2019; Hall et al., 2024). These external factors have several elements, namely, firstly, family and community environmental factors, secondly, school assignment factors, and thirdly, facilities and infrastructure factors.

To overcome the problems above, there are several solutions that we can do, including schools can increase students' interest in reading by creating methods that involve these three factors. This can be built through habituation, which can be carried out using 3 positive cultures, the first thing we can do is give rewards and punishments to students. Second, teachers should provide assignments that encourage students to utilize literacy materials in the library. Third, by preparing a library that is comfortable and easy to reach for students.

However, as time goes by, students rarely visit libraries for various reasons, including feeling lazy about dealing with the manual library

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bureaucracy of having to queue and carry loan cards and being lazy about carrying heavy books. To get around this, the school is trying to provide a digital library to further optimize learning resource services to students.

Libraries as part of schools are very important in supporting lifelong learning programs. One of the library's tasks is to provide education and information to users or visitors (Winata et al., 2021; Martzoukou, 2021; Mubofu, 2023; Chang, 2019; Radfar et al., 2020; Inskip, 2023; Tsabedze, 2020; Clarke et al., 2023; Tsabedze, 2021). One of the activities that libraries can carry out in educational activities is as a means of information literacy (Julien et al., 2018; Aharony et al., 2020; Ramgadwala, 2024; Ali et al., 2023; Son, 2024; Witt, 2024; Keshavarz, 2021).

Furthermore, in the context of libraries and information, information literacy is associated with the ability to access and utilize correctly the amount of information on the internet (Amram et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2021; Widén et al., 2023; Wann et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024; Teague, 2019; Tsunekage et al., 2019). For this reason, what users, especially school library users, need to pay attention to when utilizing internet technology is the skill of searching for information and knowing effective and efficient search strategies (Wyatt et al., 2018; Loh et al., 2021; Allard et al., 2020; Wema, 2024; Lo et al., 2019; Tajedini et al., 2020; Arpan et al., 2018; Tu-Keefner et al., 2020; Cordero et al., 2020).

From time to time, libraries have developed according to the times and the needs of their users. The library paradigm allows libraries to transform into digital libraries with the ability to access information more quickly and accurately to current human needs. Students are increasingly critical and want to access information precisely, accurately, and of course more efficiently and effectively because they do not have to queue to go to the library to borrow heavy books and with limited library service time. For this reason, a digital library system needs to be implemented.

Where this digital library is an ICT-based information provider library that provides services and collections in digital form and is accessed using the internet network (Akinola, 2022; Alzahrani et al., 2019; Aboelmaged et al.,

2024). Digital libraries as organizations that provide information sources, including staff with special expertise to select, compile, interpret, provide intellectual access, distribute, preserve, and guarantee the existence of collections of digital works over time so that these collections can be used by certain communities or selected communities economically and easily (Xie et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2019; Ruthven et al., 2023).

Collections in digital form are considered easy to store and make it easier for readers to access them via smartphone devices without any distance or time restrictions. The main aim is to provide access to all users of information, which of course is oriented toward delivering and disseminating information quickly, accurately, and reliably.

Digital libraries have various requirements, such as 1) storage and access are carried out electronically, 2) quality is guaranteed about the authority, stability, and legal certainty of the contents, 3) access and ownership are organized well, 4) intended for users, 5) financially organized, 6) good navigation facilities, effective search, and no duplication, 7) individual property rights are guaranteed and no violations occur by staff or users, 8) tracking facilities are available, control, and payment information, and 9) intervention facilities are available for help and management purposes (Winarko, 2009).

In a digital library, various features will make it easier for users to find the information they need. In its use, digital libraries have more advantages than conventional libraries, such as long-distance service, accessible, cost-effective (cheap), prevent plagiarism, and global publication (Subrata, 2009). The use of smartphones, which is now inseparable from everyday life, has forced libraries to release the latest innovations so that their users do not leave them behind.

Currently, many libraries are creating digital libraries to support their physical libraries. Some of these digital libraries use websites as their base, and some use mobile bases using operating systems such as smartphones. To optimize visits to digital libraries, it is necessary to implement an effective method to increase students' interest in accessing and reading books in digital libraries.

Thus, it is necessary to apply the SABU-SABU (one book one month) method through digital libraries, namely a method that requires all

students to read at least one book a month. In this method, students who meet the criteria will be given an award (reward) and students who do not reach the target of one book per month will be given a penalty (punishment). This aims to make students more motivated to improve their reading skills.

Assessment of students is carried out by requiring students to make a resume from the books they read. The more resumes they collect the more reading books they have completed. From here we can assess students' reading achievement. Students who do not submit a monthly reading resume will be given a warning and sanctions. The sanctions given are in the form of reading assignments and additional reading time outside of study hours or during class meetings.

METHOD

The method used in this research was qualitative analysis. The research was implemented at SMA Negeri 19 Tebo located in Tirta Kencana Village, Rimbo Bujang District, Tebo Regency, Jambi Province, Indonesia. The research population was 110 students in classes X, XI, and XII majoring in Mathematics and Natural Sciences and Social Sciences for the 2023/2024 academic year. The number of research samples was 43 students obtained using probability sampling techniques.

The data collection method used a questionnaire that was distributed to the sample. The data analysis technique used quantitative-descriptive. The needs for developing the SABU-SABU method to increase student's interest in reading at SMA Negeri 19 Tebo through a digital library which consists of 21 questions with 3 main indicators, namely, interest in reading, need for the SABU-SABU method through a digital library and perception about reading interest with 5 alternative assessments in the form of Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data collection, it was found that student's interest in reading (in general) was still low, the culture of reading books was increasingly being abandoned, and with changing media digital, it is necessary to

apply an effective method to increase student's reading interest through digital platforms. This was shown by the great interest of students in finding answers to questions and problems through digital platforms. From the results of the questionnaire, it was found that the percentage was 93% sample preferred to find solutions to problems on the internet rather than reading books manually.

Student's interest in reading was low. On the other hand, they realize that books are a window to knowledge. So, by reading diligently they will gain knowledge and experience. That was indicated by the large percentage of student's reading perception of 82%. After analyzing the tabulated data results, recommended a method that can increase student's reading interest through digital libraries.

The results of students filling out a questionnaire analyzing the needs for developing the SABU-SABU method to increase student's interest in reading at SMA Negeri 19 Tebo through a digital library are seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Results of Needs Analysis

Figure 1 showed the indicators of reading interest in general, the result was that student's reading interest was still low at 63.8%, so it needs to be increased further. This phenomenon was also supported by previous research that showed statistical data from UNESCO, out of a total of 61 countries, Indonesia was ranked 60th with a low literacy level with the last rank filled by Botswana and Thailand at rank 59, meanwhile, Finland was ranked first with a high literacy rate, almost reaching 100% (Witanto, 2018).

This data clearly showed that the high level of interest in reading in Indonesia is still far behind Singapore and Malaysia. For this reason, there needs to be a maximum effort from educators and the government to increase student's interest in reading in particular and in Indonesian society in general.

In the indicator of interest in reading, the results also showed that parental encouragement for students to get into the habit of reading was still low even though parents should be the role models for children in the family. Therefore, the role of parents in teaching reading habits is important to improve children's literacy skills.

Second, access to educational facilities is not evenly distributed and the quality of educational facilities is minimal. It is a fact that we still see many children dropping out of school, educational facilities that do not support teaching and learning activities, and long bureaucratic chains in the world of education. This is what indirectly hinders the development of literacy quality in Indonesia.

Student's low interest in reading is closely related to the level of education in the country. According to the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 43 of 2007 concerning libraries, the culture of a love of reading is carried out through families, educational units, and communities with cooperation between the government in efforts to increase interest in reading, where the government acts as the main responsible party and librarians carry out optimal performance. (www.perpusnas.go.id).

The School Literacy Movement is an activity created by the government to raise the spirit of literacy in schools, especially schools in villages. However, there may be obstacles that schools must face, namely obstacles regarding the funds that must be prepared. Insufficient funds cause the school to limit the facilities and infrastructure used for this program.

The school has a very important role in facilitating the development of student literacy to make the School Literacy Movement program a success (Agustin & Cahyono, 2017). This showed that increasing student's interest in reading was a shared responsibility between teachers, society, and the government.

The second indicator was the needs for methods to increase interest in reading. The researcher intends to introduce a new method, namely a method that requires students to read one book a month, called SABU-SABU. The use of this term was expected to attract student's attention by arousing curiosity to find out more about the aims and objectives of this method. This method was developed using a

digital library to make it easier for readers to access literacy sources.

As we all know, our young generation now prefers to carry smartphones everywhere rather than having to carry books which are heavy, inconvenient, and require quite a lot of time and energy-consuming administration to visit the library manually. This was supported by the results of a questionnaire which showed that students prefer to seek information from the internet rather than books, with a percentage more than 78%. For this reason, the SABU-SABU method needs to be applied to increase student's interest in reading at SMA Negeri 19 Tebo.

The third indicator, namely regarding perceived interest in reading, this indicator has a high percentage, at 82%, which showed quite high awareness of the benefits of reading even though students themselves have low interest in reading. This was proven by the results of the questionnaire instrument on the question which states that reading will open up my thinking discourse, the results showed a high figure, at 87.4%.

From this, we can understand that even though student's interest in reading was relatively low, students have the awareness that reading will increase their knowledge. For this reason, what we need to do is create an effective and fun method to increase student's reading interest. We can do this by implementing the SABU-SABU method through digital libraries.

CONCLUSION

According to the results and discussion, it was concluded that student's interest in reading at SMA Negeri 19 Tebo was still low, as well as motivation from parents was still low. However, the perception of student's reading interest was high. This showed that it is necessary to take action or action to increase student's reading interest. For this reason, it is necessary to apply an appropriate and effective method that can increase reading interest in the form of the SABU-SABU method. This method will motivate students to increase their interest in reading because there exists reward and punishment in its application. The SABU-SABU method through digital libraries is considered to be very necessary for its implementation because today's students prefer to search for information from the internet rather than through manual

books. Students also prefer to access information from their own devices because it is more effective compared to having to borrow books from the library with a series of administration that must be completed. Borrowing books on a digital platform is considered simpler than borrowing books manually at the library.

REFERENCES

- Aboelimged, M., Mouakket, S., & Ali, I. (2024). A scientometric analysis of digital library adoption over the past 30 years: Models, trends, and research directions. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 56(3), 809-828. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09610006231161143>.
- Agustin, S., & Cahyono, B. E. H. (2017). Gerakan literasi sekolah untuk meningkatkan budaya baca di SMA Negeri 1 Geger. *Linguista: Jurnal Ilmiah Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pembelajarannya*, 1(2), 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.25273/linguista.v1i2.1973>.
- Aharony, N., Julien, H., & Nadel-Kritz, N. (2020). Survey of information literacy instructional practices in academic libraries. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 52(4), 964-971. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000619891762>.
- Akinola, S. A. (2022). Management of academic library services in the 21st century digital dispensation. *Alexandria*, 32(2), 90-104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09557490231217714>.
- Ali, N., Shoaib, M., & Abdullah, F. (2023). Information literacy and research support services in academic libraries: A bibliometric analysis from 2001 to 2020. *Journal of Information Science*, 49(6), 1593-1606. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211068169>.
- Allard, B., Lo, P., Liu, Q., Ho, K. K. W., Chiu, D. K. W., Chen, J. C. C., Zhou, Q., & Jiang, T. (2020). LIS pre-professionals' perspectives towards library user education: A comparative study between three universities in Greater China. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 52(3), 832-852. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000619874106>.
- Alzahrani, A. I., Mahmud, I., Ramayah, T., Alfarraj, O., & Alalwan, N. (2019). Modelling digital library success using the DeLone and McLean information system success model. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 51(2), 291-306. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000617726123>.
- Amram, S. B., Aharony, N., & Ilan, J. B. (2021). Information literacy education in primary schools: A case study. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 53(2), 349-364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000620938132>.
- Arpan, M., Budiman, R. D. A., & Jalinus, N. (2018). Usulan sistem pengolahan data siswa di SMP Harapan Ananda Kubu Raya. *Jurnal Pendidikan Informatika dan Sains*, 7(2), 271-280.
- Boerma, I. E., Mol, S. E., & Jolles, J. (2018). Parents adjust the quality of their home literacy environment to the reading interest of their third to sixth graders. *Parenting*, 18(4), 243-261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15295192.2018.1524243>.
- Chang, Y.-W. (2019). A comparison of researcher-practitioner collaborations in library and information science, education, and sociology. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 51(1), 208-217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000617726121>.
- Clarke, R. I., Grimm, A., Zhang, B., & Stanton, K. L. (2023). Time, tasks, and toll: Changes in library work during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Library Administration*, 63(4), 421-445. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01930826.2023.2201717>.
- Cordero, K., Chiuminatto, P., Duncan, S., & Vera, E. (2020). Millennials in the stacks: Choices, habits and attitudes of frequent library users between the ages of 18-29 in Santiago, Chile. *The International Information & Library Review*, 53(1), 15-34.

- <https://doi.org/10.1080/10572317.2020.1786794>.
- Hall, G. J., Nelson, P. M., & Parker, D. C. (2024). What environments support reading growth among current compared with former reading intervention recipients? A multilevel analysis of students and their schools. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 2024(April). <https://doi.org/10.1177/00222194241236164>.
- Hebbecke, K., Förster, N., & Souvignier, E. (2019). Reciprocal effects between reading achievement and intrinsic and extrinsic reading motivation. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 23(5), 419-436. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2019.1598413>.
- Holbert, R. M. G. (2019). Quick fix: Using the circle question format to promote pre-reading for individual and collaborative critical thinking. *College Teaching*, 67(2), 83-85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87567555.2018.1558167>.
- Huang, S., Han, Z., Yang, B., & Ren, N. (2019). Factor identification and computation in the assessment of information security risks for digital libraries. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 51(1), 78-94. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000616668572>.
- Inskip, C. (2023). What are the options for library and information studies education reform in addressing racial inequity in the library profession in the UK? *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 55(4), 972-998. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09610006221114483>.
- Ives, S. T., Parsons, S. A., Cutter, D., Field, S. A., Wells, M. S., & Lague, M. (2022). Intrinsic and extrinsic reading motivation: Context, theory, and measurement. *Reading Psychology*, 44(3), 306-325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2022.2141403>.
- Julien, H., Gross, M., & Latham, D. (2018). Survey of information literacy instructional practices in U.S. academic libraries. *College & Research Libraries*, 79(2), 179-199. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.79.2.179>.
- Kanonire, T., Lubenko, J., & Kuzmina, Y. (2020). The effects of intrinsic and extrinsic reading motivation on reading performance in elementary school. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 36(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02568543.2020.1822961>.
- Keshavarz, H. (2021). Entrepreneurial capabilities of librarians in university libraries: A cross-contextual study on the impact of information literacy. *Journal of Business & Finance Librarianship*, 26(3), 200-222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08963568.2021.1941576>.
- Li, J. T., Arizmendi, G. D., & Swanson, H. L. (2022). The influence of teachers' math instructional practices on English learners' reading comprehension and math problem-solving performance in Spanish and English. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 25(10), 3614-3630. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2022.2068346>.
- Link, E., Henke, J., & Möhring, W. (2021). Credibility and enjoyment through data? Effects of statistical information and data visualizations on message credibility and reading experience. *Journalism Studies*, 22(5), 575-594. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2021.1889398>.
- Lo, P., Ho, K. K. W., Allard, B., Horng, S.-C., & Liu, Y. (2019). Reading the city via the public central library in the sociocultural context: A comparative study between the Hong Kong Central Library, Shanghai Library and Taipei Public Library. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 51(2), 458-472. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000617742448>.
- Locher, F. M., Becker, S., & Pfof, M. (2019). The relation between students' intrinsic reading motivation and book reading in recreational and school contexts. *AERA Open*, 5(2), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2332858419852041>.

- Loh, C. E., Hamarian, E. B. M., Qi, L. L. Y., Lim, Q., & Zee, S. N. Y. (2021). Developing future-ready school libraries through design thinking: A case study. *IFLA Journal*, 47(4), 505-519. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352211028897>.
- Martzoukou, K. (2021). Academic libraries in Covid-19: a renewed mission for digital literacy. *Library Management*, 42(4), 266-276. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-09-2020-0131>.
- Miyamoto, A. (2023). A role of gender in the reciprocal relations between intrinsic reading motivation and reading comprehension. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 28(3), 256-269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2023.2260032>.
- Mohammadi, R. R., Saeidi, M., Ahangari, S., & Hui, S. K. F. (2020). Self-regulated learning instruction and the relationships among self-regulation, reading comprehension and reading problem solving: PLS-SEM approach. *Cogent Education*, 7(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2020.1746105>.
- Mohseni, F., Seifoori, Z., Ahangari, S., & Khajavi, Y. (2020). The impact of metacognitive strategy training and critical thinking awareness-raising on reading comprehension. *Cogent Education*, 7(1), 23-44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2020.1720946>.
- Mubofu, C. (2023). Experiences, purposes, satisfaction and missing library services as predictors of library information services provision: A case study. *Alexandria*, 33(1), 64-79. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09557490241244747>.
- Ng, W. S., Wong, T. T. Y., & Fong, C. Y. C. (2021). Contributions of reading comprehension subskills to arithmetic word-problem solving among Chinese primary school students. *Journal of Cognition and Development*, 22(4), 585-604. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2021.1916498>.
- Öztürk, M., Akkan, Y., & Kaplan, A. (2019). Reading comprehension, Mathematics self-efficacy perception, and Mathematics attitude as correlates of students' non-routine Mathematics problem-solving skills in Turkey. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 51(7), 1042-1058. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2019.1648893>.
- Radfar, A. H., Fahimnia, F., Esmaili, M. R., & Beheshti, M. A-S. (2020). Semantic modeling for education of library and information sciences in Iran, based on Soft Systems Methodology. *IFLA Journal*, 46(3), 271-289. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0340035219881641>.
- Ramgadwala, H. (2024). Impact of multimedia on academic information literacy instruction in libraries. *IFLA Journal*, 50(2), 273-291. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352231222042>.
- Ruthven, I., Robinson, E., & McMenemy, D. (2023). The value of digital and physical library services in UK public libraries and why they are not interchangeable. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 55(4), 1143-1154. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09610006221127027>.
- Son, S. (2024). Libraries' roles in media and information literacy education: Obtaining the opinions of South Korean volunteer librarians through the Delphi method. *IFLA Journal*, 2024(June), 22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352241252922>.
- Subrata, G. (2009). *Perpustakaan Digital*. Malang: Universitas Negeri Malang.
- Tajedini, O., Khasseh, A. A., Afzali, M., & Sadatmoosavi, A. (2020). How to increase the loyalty of public library users? A qualitative study. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 52(2), 317-330. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000619856081>.
- Teague, D. P. (2019). Tips for teaching library instruction and information literacy to first-gen college students, nontraditional students, or English as a second language (ESL) students. *Serials Review*, 45(3), 105-110.

- <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2019.1644699>.
- Toste, J. R., Didion, L., Peng, P., Filderman, M. J., & McClelland, A. M. (2020). A meta-analytic review of the relations between motivation and reading achievement for K-12 students. *Review of Educational Research, 90*(3), 420-456. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320919352>.
- Tsabedze, V. (2020). Toward a Framework for quality assurance of library and information science education in an open distance e-learning environment in Eswatini. *Journal of Library & Information Services in Distance Learning, 14*(2), 160-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533290X.2020.1806176>.
- Tsabedze, V. (2021). MOOCs and OER: A model for library and information science education. *Internet Reference Services Quarterly, 25*(3), 87-106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10875301.2021.1930621>.
- Tsunekage, T., Bishop, C. R., Long, C. M., & Levin, I. I. (2019). Integrating information literacy training into an inquiry-based introductory biology laboratory. *Journal of Biological Education, 54*(4), 396-403. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00219266.2019.1600569>.
- Tu-Keefner, F., Liu, J., Lyons, D., Hobbs, A., Smith, J. C., & Corbo, M. (2020). Disaster health information access and public libraries' situation-specific information services: What public librarians and library users said. *Journal of Consumer Health on the Internet, 24*(3), 201-227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15398285.2020.1791666>.
- Wang, L., Lee, H., & Ju, D. Y. (2018). Impact of digital content on young children's reading interest and concentration for books. *Behaviour & Information Technology, 38*(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2018.1502807>.
- Wang, Q., Ma, M., Shi, Y., Li, M., & Wang, T. (2023). Modeling the relationships among home literacy environment, reading interest, self-regulation, and reading ability of children with intellectual disabilities in China. *International Journal of Developmental Disabilities, 70*(5), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20473869.2023.2230411>.
- Wang, R., Wu, C., Wang, X., Xu, F., & Yuan, Q. (2024). E-tourism information literacy and its role in driving tourist satisfaction with online travel information: A qualitative comparative analysis. *Journal of Travel Research, 63*(4), 904-922. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00472875231177229>.
- Wann, T., Khongtim, J., & Chyne, R. C. (2024). Assessing the impact of information literacy on farmers' decision-making processes: A mixed-methods approach. *IFLA Journal, 2024*(July). <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352241261730>.
- Wema, E. F. (2024). The role of Tanzania library services board in enhancing information literacy skills among the public in Tanzania. *Information Development, 40*(3), 398-413. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02666669221123039>.
- Widén, G., Ahmad, F., & Huvila, I. (2023). Connecting information literacy and social capital to better utilise knowledge resources in the workplace. *Journal of Information Science, 49*(6), 1481-1492. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211060531>.
- Widiana, I. W., Triyono, S., Sudirtha, I. G., Adijaya, M. A., & Wulandari, I. G. A. A. M. (2023). Bloom's revised taxonomy-oriented learning activity to improve reading interest and creative thinking skills. *Cogent Education, 10*(2), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2221482>.
- Winarko, B. (2009). Perpustakaan digital di Indonesia dan fitur-fitur yang tersedia. *Jurnal Perpustakaan Pertanian, 18*(2), 45.
- Winata, A. P., Fadelina, R., & Basuki, S. (2021). New normal and library services in Indonesia: a case study of university libraries. *Digital Library Perspectives, 37*(1), 77-84. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-07-2020-0059>.
- Witanto, J. (2018). *Minat baca yang sangat*

- rendah*. Salatiga: Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Kristen Satya Wacana Salatiga.
- Witt, S. (2024). Libraries leading the way: Sustainability, information literacy, and community engagement. *IFLA Journal*, 2024(September), 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352241283305>.
- Wyatt, D., Mcquire, S., & Butt, D. (2018). Libraries as redistributive technology: From capacity to culture in Queensland's public library network. *New Media & Society*, 20(8), 2934-2953. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444817738235>.
- Xie, I., Joo, S., & Matusiak, K. K. (2021). Digital library evaluation measures in academic settings: Perspectives from scholars and practitioners. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 53(1), 130-152. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000620935505>.
- Yulian, R. (2021). The flipped classroom: Improving critical thinking for critical reading of EFL learners in higher education. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(2), 508-522. <https://doi.org/10.24815/siele.v8i2.18366>.
- Zhao, W., Song, Y., Zhao, Q., & Zhang, R. (2018). The effect of teacher support on primary school students' reading engagement: the mediating role of reading interest and Chinese academic self-concept. *Educational Psychology*, 39(2), 236-253. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2018.1497146>.
- Zhu, S., Yang, H. H., Wu, D., & Chen, F. (2021). Investigating the Relationship Between Information Literacy and Social Media Competence Among University Students. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 59(7), 1425-1449. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633121997360>.